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EFFECTS OF ANTHROPOGENIC ACTIVITIES ON VEGETATION CHANGES IN GUINEA SAVANNA REGION OF NIGERIA- A CASE OF EDU LOCAL GOVERNMENT, KWARA STATE

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Abstract: *This work examined effects of anthropogenic activities on vegetation changes in Guinea savanna region of Edu Local Government Kwara State, Nigeria. There are various economic activities going on in the region and these activities have significantly contributed to the changes in the vegetation cover of the study area. Erdas Imagine 2015 was for computerizing NDVI, ArcMap version 10.5 for images extraction; mapping of study area and NDVI mapping; ArcMap 10.5 for the conversion of the images (vector) to raster and excel for the calculation percentages and graphs. Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) were used as method for detecting any form of changes in Edu local government open forest. NDVI result shows (-0.26) which indicates a decrease in vegetation cover in the study area. The vegetation index Map of 1990, 2005-2018 also shows that there is further decrease in vegetation (0.58) (0.48) in 1990 and 2005 respectively. NDVI values of (0.35) indicated a decline in the vegetation of 2005 -2018(0.48) (0.35) respectively. The patches of thick green colour of 1990, 2005 and 2018 images show continual decreased of forest from 1990-2018. The shrubs continue to expand from 1990-2018. This means that, there is sharp decline in the Forests cover between the intervals of another fifteen years. Tree planting campaign should be undertaken through print and electronic media, public and private owned radio stations. The campaign should educate recent flood events that ravaged the region.*

Keywords: Effects, Anthropogenic, Vegetation, Guinea Savanna, NDVI

INTRODUCTION

Man's quest to satisfy his needs have put enormous pressure on the forest's resources in Nigeria, the desire to get foods, cloths and shelters keep growing with the increase in population and these trends is persistence. This is not only through subsistence farming system but also commercial Agriculture. Agricultural practices have done a lot of damages to the forest cover the world over. Forestry resources is been threatened due to urbanization going on at an increasing rate and competing for the available space. Conversion of forest into

small-scale agriculture accounts for nearly two thirds of all tropical forest destruction (FAO, 2008). Some scientists insist that it means a complete change from forest to agriculture urban areas or deserts; others include logging activities, according to Food and agricultural organization FAO, (2008). Keller and Bolkin (2007) observed that, as the human population grows, the use of firewood increases. Management of the of wood stands is essential to improve forest growth and a well-planned management of firewood has been the exception rather than the rule. Tree affects the

earth by evaporating water, slowing erosion and providing habitat for wildlife. Trees also affect climate. To this end there is need for proactive measures to be put in place in order halt, or to reverse the trend and permanently correct the damages already been done to the environment. Laah (2018), observed that besides the emission of greenhouse gases, a number of human activities have altered earth' energy balance through changes in land use. The clearing of vegetation for road or housing

construction could lead to changes in the reflectivity of the earth's surface. This will affect the amount of sunlight that is reflected back into space. Some pollutants from industrial and agricultural concerns produce aerosol, and because aerosols affect cloud formation, they can have a warming or cooling effect on the Earth depending on the location. Other pollutants like black carbon particles (or 'soot') which are product of the burning of fossils fuels and vegetation can also lead to warming of the Earth because they absorb incoming solar radiation.

Figure 1.1: Edu Local Government Area

Source: Author, 2019

Edu, the study in this investigation, is located between longitudes 4°54'15"East and 5° 31' 00" of the Greenwich meridian and latitudes 8° 35' 38" and 9° 15' 00" of the Equator (Figure 1). It covers an area of 2,542 km². It is one of the sixteen Local Government Areas in Kwara State with Lafiagi as the headquarters. The Local Government Area has a population of 201,469 as reported in the 2006 population census. It has three administrative districts: Lafiagi, Tsaragi, and Shonga. The study area has a mean annual rainfall and temperature of 300 mm and 29°C respectively, (Bello and Makinde, 2007). The Average Relative Humidity is about 78.6 % and this varies seasonally with the lowest value of 69.99 %. The study area is characterized by the alternate dry and wet season. Raining season in the area starts towards the end of March and lasts till October while dry season commences in November and ends in early March

Edu LGA is dominated by Nupe speaking people; they live close to river banks and engage in agriculture as the major economic activity. Fish farming and rice cultivation are the two major activities of the people in the study area. The study area comprises of three districts with different vegetation zones. Few examples of the forests found in the region includes kusoko forest, Cheko/Shaban, Wode Nuwan. Patiketsan and, Kusozhiko,

The residents of the areas engaged in farming, fishing and commercial activities as their major occupation. Some work with Lafiagi Sugar Company and Valentine Chicken located in Shonga to earn a living.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

DATA COLLECTION

This study used the Landsat imageries for 1990, 2005, and 2018 downloaded from USGS explorer. Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) was used for detecting any form of changes in the imageries. This followed José

et al. (2009) observation that the created NDVI images identified could be used to identify the pattern of changes that had occurred between two different dates

Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) has been used in the studies such as Agone and Bhamare, (2012) and Alhassan *et al.* (2014) stated that it is a measure of vegetation vigor, which provides an effective measure of photo synthetically active biomass, and it is calculated as follows.

$$NDVI = (NIR - R) / (NIR + R)$$

Where NIR and Red are spectral reflectance values in the near infrared and visible red band respectively. After determining the four NDVI maps for the four years, the mapped NDVI change analysis and NDVI difference between 1990 and 2018 were done by comparing the four NDVI maps for determining the spatio-temporal changes. The hardware's used in this studies includes, GPS digital scanner a and measuring tape. Other softwares includes Several materials were used to collect the data and for data analysis. The following equipment were used: GPS, Digital camera, 100 meters measuring tape, questionnaires, pencil, and pen. The following software's was used: Erdas Imagine 2015 for computerizing NDVI.

ArcMap version10.5 for images extraction, mapping of study area and NDVI mapping. ArcMap 10.5 for the conversion of the images (vector) to raster. Excel for the calculations of percentage and for the graphs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 1 to 3 show the Normalized Vegetation Index (NDVI) of Edu Local Government for the year 1990, 2015 and 2018. The NDVI values for 1990 range from -0.26 to 0.56, while the NDVI values for 2005 range from -0.23 to 0.48 and the 2018 NDVI values range from -0.11 to 0.35.

NDVI values which range from -0.26 to 0.56 indicates a high biomass. As at this time, Edu Local Government Forest was natural plantation which signified that the Edu Local Government Forest was in natural form devoid of human interference. However, the figures show the vegetation reflectance as negative (-0.26) which indicates a decrease in the greenness of the area.

This result affirmed the earlier findings of Njoku (2008) revealed an apparent negative trend of vegetation vigor in the South Eastern Nigeria with NDVI deficit of -0.5 to -0.7 between 1970 and 1980s and a concomitant loss of 78% (166,338m²) vegetation cover. Furthermore, Njoku (2008) stated that Nigeria forest areas have diminished from about 60 million hectares in 1890 to the current value of about 9.6million hectares.

Figure 2: NDVI values of Edu Local Government Forest Resource for 1990
 Source: Authors (2019)

Figure 2 shows that the vegetation reflectance of Edu Local Government Forest for the year 2005 have NDVI values which range from - 0.23 to 0.48. The highest NDVI value of 0.48 indicates comparatively dense vegetation when compared to the 1990 NDVI -0.23.

Figure 3: NDVI values of Edu Local Government Forest Resource for 2018
 Source: Authors work (2019)

Figure 3 shows the vegetation reflectance of the study area for the year 2018, as depicted in figure 3. It shows that year 2018 have NDVI values which range from -0.11 to 0.35. The

very high NDVI value 0.35 indicates comparative dense vegetation when compared with -0.11.

Figure 4: NDVI value of Edu Local Government Forest Resources
Source ;Aauthor 2019

Figure 4 shows the different NDVI changes of Edu local Government Forest period. Although the changes occurred in all classes but important changes occurred only in 2018 in all classes. The category of very high NDVI density has decreased from 0.56 in 1990 to 0.48 in 2005. Similarly, the category of very high NDVI density has drastically decreased from 0.48 in 2005 to 0.35 in 2018. The category of high NDVI density also decreased from 0.32 in 1990 to 0.21 in 2005 and further decreased to 0.14 in 2018. The most significant reduction in greenness in the study area however occurred in all classes in 2018.

The deep green colour of 1990, 2005 and 2018 which shows presence of thick forest decrease continually from 1990-2018. While the light

green colour which indicates shrubs and grasses regrowth expanded between 1999 and 2018. The orange colour further indicates dramatic changes to forest cover with only presence of grasses and farmlands. The red colour shown in the three figures shows bare grounds where vegetation's are completely eliminated due to different economic activities in the area. This implies that forest resources in the area are seriously threatened due to different anthropogenic activities. This trend is predicted to continue in the study area unless serious interventions are taken to halt this negative impact of anthropogenic activities. The implication of this is climate change and global warming effect will continue to rise. Thus, there is the need to take a bold step to remedy the situations.

Figure 5: Edu Local Government Forest change detection during 1990, 2005 and 2018
 Source: Anthon, 2019

CONCLUSION

Vegetation in the study area has greatly reduced due to anthropogenic activities such as farming, firewood fetching, logging, and charcoal production as shown in the study. Urbanization and building construction, commercial farming (BUA Sugar Company, Abiola Farms and Bacita Sugar Company and Zimbabwe Farm) has greatly impacted negatively on the vegetation of the area. Subsistence farming activities across the three districts is amongst the major factors of forests degradation. Large areas of virgin land have been degraded and people are forced to move to neighbouring Local Governments for farming.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. **Planting of tree crops:** such as mango guava cashew orange and citrus trees should be encouraged. This action will not only encourage reforestation but will also improve the economic condition of the residents of the areas.
2. **Tree planting campaign:** should be promoted by relevant government agencies publicized by the Government in radio, print and electronic media, by the Government prints and electronic media. Reasons for the recent floods' events should be explained to the residents through these sources. Attempting such as this will no doubt go a long way to change the narration.
3. Public enlightenment through seminars and symposium should be regularly undertaken. This should incorporate community Leaders, traditional rulers, and general public. Lectures to be given here should cover benefits of tree planting and effect of trees on climate change. There is every possibility that majority of the participants will carry the message home

and this will no doubt help to change the perception of the members of the Community on the forest's destruction.

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